

EVALUATION OF ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF SOME MEDICINAL PLANTS ON COMMON ENTERIC FOOD-BORNE PATHOGENS

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ABSTRACT

Enterobacteria are often responsible for various gastrointestinal food borne infection in humans especially in the developing countries. *Cassia occidentalis*, *Croton zambesicus* and *Newbouldia leavis* known as 'Ewe ori esi', Ajekobale and Akoko respectively in Yoruba are three plants whose leaves are used in combination by boiling to treat gastrointestinal and diarrhea illnesses among indigenes of Akungba-Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria. The leave extracts from these medicinal plants were screened *in vitro* in the laboratory for their antibacterial activity against two prominent enteric bacteria, that is, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* using the agar disc diffusion method. The tyndalized leave extract of *Croton zambesicus* showing antibacterial inhibition zone of 4mm and 2mm against *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Escherichia coli* respectively exhibited highest activity during the study than the autoclaved samples and other plant sources tested independently or combined, showing that the combinations of the extract samples do not exhibit synergistic effects. *Croton zambesicus* can however be optimized clinically for chemotherapeutic control of these food-borne enteric infections.

KEY WORDS: Antimicrobial, Enterobacteria, Evaluation, Food-borne, Pathogens, Plants.

INTRODUCTION

Enteric bacteria are major causes of food-borne illnesses and gastrointestinal problems in the developing countries and human beings around the world. The most common agents are *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* but *Shigella* species and other species of *Salmonella* also have been implicated in a significant number of cases (Stainer *et. al.*, 1987). Symptoms of foodborne illnesses range from stomach upset to more serious symptoms including diarrhoea, vomiting, abdominal cramps and fever. In some people, especially children, haemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) can occur from infection by a particular strain of *Escherichia coli* 0157:117 and can lead to kidney failure and death (NIH, 2003).

Vehicle of transmission of these etiologic agents are mainly food and water. Many disease-causing organisms of medical importance have developed resistance to antibiotics. Palombo and Sample (2001) suggests there is a distinct and constant need for safe and more efficient therapeutic agent. A way out of reducing antibiotic resistance and adverse effects on host is the employment of antibiotic resistance inhibitors of plant origin (Nostro *et. al.*, 2000; Kim *et. al.*, 1995). Chariantly *et. al.*, (1999) stated that plant-derived medicines have been part of traditional health care in most parts of the world for thousands of years and there is increasing interest in them as sources of agents to fight microbial diseases. Aburjai *et. al.*, (2001) also confirms folkloric accounts in literatures on the use of variety of plant preparations for the treatment of infections.

Clinically, antibiotics produced by soil microorganisms and higher plants have been known sources of antibiotics (Trease *et. al.*, 1972). According to Charles and Simmon (1992), the use of medicinal plants also contributes significantly to primary health care in various parts of the world.

Cassia occidentalis, *Croton zambesicus* and *Newbouldia leavis* known as 'Ewe ori esi', Ajekobale and Akoko respectively in Yoruba are three plants whose leaves are used in combination by boiling to treat gastrointestinal and diarrhea illnesses. Similar crude extracts of the leaves of these plants were used both independently and in combinations to investigate their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium*

Enteric bacteria belong to the family enterobacteriaceae, which are large group of Gram negative, peritrichously flagellated or non-flagellated straight rods with simple nutritional requirements. They grow

Table 1: Some biochemical characteristics of enterobacteria used

Biochemical Test	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	<i>Escherichia Coli</i>
Cultural characteristics on EMB agar	Dark smooth colony	Green metallic sheen
Gram stain	-	-
Shape	Shortrod	Shortrod
Catalase test	+	+
Citrate utilization	+	-
Lactose fermentation	-	+
Indole production	-	+
Motility	+	+
Presumptive confirmation of test isolates	+	+

best under aerobic condition but also ferment carbohydrates by an anaerobic pathway (Prescott *et. al.*, 2002). Enterobacteria include coliforms like *E.coli* and other Gram-negative enteric flora, Non-fermenters that are non-lactose fermenting or slow lactose fermenting bacterial which could be either normal flora or regular pathogens also forms part of the enteric organisms (Talaro and Talaro, 1996).

Enteric infections remain a leading cause of childhood mortality in developing countries. It has been reported that enteric pathogens are the most frequent cause of diarrhea illnesses that account for an animal mortality rate of 5 million people worldwide (Bennish, 2004). And prominent pathogenic enterics include *Salmonella*, *Shigella* and strains of *Escherichia coli* (Talaro and Talaro, 1996).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Microorganisms used

Pure cultures *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* were obtained from the University College Hospital, University of Ibadan and the School of Medical Laboratory Science, Obafemi Awolowo Teaching Hospital, Ile-Ife respectively. The organisms were further identified and maintained in stock culture at 4°C.

Culture media

Tryptone soy agar, Eosin methylene blue (EMB) agar and Nutrient agar were generally used during the study. Tryptone soy agar was used for the antimicrobial tests and EMB cultures distinguish the lactose-fermenting bacteria, which produces dark colonies, or green metallic sheen (as exhibited by most *E.coli* species), while non-lactose fermenters appeared colourless. Nutrient agar was routinely used for stock cultures and subculturing.

Plant materials screened

The plants used for the study includes *Cassia occidentalis*, *Croton zambesicus* and *Newbouldia laevis* wild crafted locally in Akungba-Akoko township, Ondo State Nigeria. The leaves from this plant sources were washed with clean water and 50 grams of the leaves were milled or blended with 500 ml distilled water with the aid of an electric blender.

The blended samples were divided into two portions and sterilized separately. First at 121°C for 15 minutes and the second portion was tyndalized for 3 days at 70°C for 30 minutes each day. It was then concentrated at 70 °C in the oven after sterilization.

In vitro antimicrobial test

The disc agar diffusion described by Nostro *et. al.*, (2000), Xavier *et. al.*, (2003) and Ajayi (2006) was used to determine growth inhibition pattern of bacteria by the plant extracts. A loopful of the test organisms

Table 2: Antibacterial activity of plant extracts against *Salmonella typhi*

Plant extracts	Zones of inhibition (<i>S. typhi</i>)			
	Autoclaved		Tyndalized	
	S.D.T	D.D.T	S.D.T	D.D.T
<i>Cassia occidentalis</i>	++	+++	-	+
<i>Croton zambensis</i>	+	+++	++	++++
<i>Newbouldia leavis</i>	+	++	+	++
C.C.N	++	++	++	++
Distilled water	-	-	-	-

Legend: ++: 1mm ++: 2mm +++: 3mm ++++: 4mm

S.D.T: Single disc test D.D.T: Double disc test

Extract – C.C.N is the combination of *C.occidentalis*, *C. zambensis* *N. leavis*

from broth cultures was diluted and evenly spread by streaking on the Tryptone Soy Agar plates under aseptic condition.

Paper disc impregnated with the sterilized plant extracts and other different concentrations of extracts were placed with the aid of sterile forceps at equidistant on the plating culture. Discs dipped in sterilized distilled water served as control. The samples were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours and examined for zones of growth inhibition and the diameter of these zones were measured in millimeters.

RESULT

The strains of *Salmonella typhi* and *Escherichia coli* used were identified by standard microbiological method as shown in table 1. The antimicrobial pattern of the plant extracts studied was demonstrated in Table 2, whereby *Cassia occidentalis* and *Croton zambensis* had higher activity of 3 mm and 4 mm zone of antimicrobial activity respectively during the study compared with other samples tested with lower values. The highest value of 4 mm zone of antibacterial inhibition demonstrated by *C.zambensis* outweighs the use of the combined plant extracts of *C. occidentalis*, *C. zambensis* and *N. leavis* with 2 mm zone of inhibition.

In table 3,the result shows that most of the plants extracts were less effective against the strain of *E.coli* tested except, *C. zambensis* which had the highest antibacterial inhibition zone of 2 mm. The tyndalized combined extract similarly showed the same effect under this context.

DISCUSSION

Cassia occidentalis and *Croton zambensis* exhibited active antimicrobial activity against the enterobacteria tested that is, *S.typhi* and *E.coli* than *N.leavis* and the combination of the three plant sources. However the *C.zambensis* was most active when tyndalized before use showing the 4mm and 2mm zone of inhibition against *S.typhi* and *E. coli* respectively, which was the highest during the study. Ashbir and Ashenati (1999) demonstrated that excessive heating like that experienced during sterilization at 121°C for 15 minutes during this study could affect some thermo-labile biological active substances in plants. Based on this and result obtained in this study, the tyndalized plant extracts could be much more relevant for use as antimicrobial agent to maintain the plant ingredients activity.

Synergistic effect experienced in combination of some plant sources for use as antimicrobial agent described by Farnsworths *et. al.*,(1966), does not work out effectively in this study because the combined extract showed 2mm zone of microbial inhibition which is lower value compared with that from *C. zambensis* alone (Table 2). Thus, the use of this single plant source is recommended for use against the combined usage practiced among the indigenes of Akungba-Akoko. The trial of the double disc test gives much more distinct result for the test.

Future research on this study can however concentrate on optimizing clinically the chemotherapeutic processes of *Croton zambensis* for treatment and control of this common food-borne enteric infections like typhoid in Akungba-Akoko and other parts of the country where the plants can be easily cultivated or otherwise commercialized for pharmaceutical purpose.

Table 3: Antibacterial activity of plant extracts against *Escherichia coli*

Plant extracts	Zones of inhibition (<i>E. coli</i>)			
	Autoclaved		Tyndalized	
	S.D.T	D.D.T	S.D.T	D.D.T
<i>Cassia occidentalis</i>	-	++	-	-
<i>Croton zambensis</i>	+++*	++	+++*	++
<i>Newbouldia leavis</i>	-	-	-	-
C.C.N	-	-	+++*	++
Distilled water	-	-	-	-

Legend: +: 1mm ++: 2mm +++: 3mm ++++: 4mm

*: Faint zone of inhibition

S.D.T: Single disc test D.D.T: Double disc test

Extract – C.C.N is the combination of *C.occidentalis*, *C. zambensis* *N. leavis*

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